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AUTHOR:	Felix Seidel, Florian Schneider, Daria Seitz, Axel Don
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Report on the area of implementation of selected agricultural measures, their definitions and the calculation of the tier 2 C sequestration potential

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Name	Institute
Jonathan Holland	AFBI
Lisa Makoschitz	AGES
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Claudio Mondini, Francesco Galioto, Irene Criscuoli, Roberta Farina	CREA
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Ivana Galuskova	CZU
Bert Reubens, Greet Ruyschaert, Ioanna S. Panagea, Kaat Mertens, Paul Pardon	ILVO
Jose A Rodriguez	INIA
Ana Paz, Corina Carranca, Nadia Castanheira	INIAV
Florent Levavasseur, Katja Klumpp, Manuel Martin	INRAE
Ieva Mockeviciene	LAMMC
Alice Budai, Daniel Rasse	NIBIO
Rastislav Skalsky	NPPC
Rong Lang, Thomas Kätterer	SLU
Ulfet Erdal, Zeynep Demir	TAGEM
David Emde, Mirjam Helfrich	Thünen
Stefan Koco	UNIPO
Erik Rihter	University Agriculture Center, Slovenia
Jan Peter Lesschen	WUR
Ana Paz, Corina Carranca, Nadia Castanheira	INIAV
Florent Levavasseur, Katja Klumpp, Manuel Martin	INRAE

Report on the area of implementation of selected agricultural measures, their definitions and the calculation of the tier 2 C sequestration potential

Executive summary

This report outlines the process and findings of the EJP SOIL-CarboSeq project, which aims to estimate achievable carbon (C) sequestration potentials for European agricultural mineral soils. The focus is on defining agricultural measures that potentially sequester C in soils (Part I), associated areas where these measures can be implemented additionally (Part II) and finally quantifying the C sequestration potential of each measure through novel European emission factors (Part III).

Part I provides an overview of selected agricultural measures that potentially lead to C sequestration in European agricultural soils, including technical solutions (tillage practices, irrigation, biochar application), optimized crop rotations (perennial legumes and temporary ley management, cover crops, crop residues management), and additional woody vegetation in the agricultural landscape.

Part II focuses on defining the area where these measures can be additionally implemented using a harmonized framework applied to all EU-27 and/or EJP SOIL member countries resulting in the theoretical area of implementation representing all agricultural mineral soils within Europe. This theoretical area is then refined based on biophysical, technical, and other constraints to determine the feasible area of implementation for each measure. Tillage practices, biochar application and increased cover cropping are those measures covering the largest area followed by irrigation, crop residue management, woody vegetation and perennial legumes and temporary ley management.

In part III C sequestration potentials have been quantified based on the definitions, area of implementation and novel European emission factors. Biochar application was identified as the measure with the highest potential for carbon sequestration in European agriculture, followed by woody vegetation, tillage practices, and crop rotation measures. Implementing these measures could potentially compensate greenhouse gas emissions from European agriculture by up to 32% annually for a limited period of time.

Biochar application: Carbon sequestration with biochar is easy to quantify and persistent due to its very slow degradation and suitability for large areas. However, its production is currently limited by existing capacities of pyrolysis plants and the availability of feedstock. For most European soils the additional benefits (higher yield, higher water storage capacity, less N₂O emissions) are small or negligible.

Woody vegetation: Provides significant carbon sequestration potential in both soil and biomass, making it the second most effective measure. Multiple other environmental benefits are provided by this measure.

Tillage practices and crop rotation measures: These measures contribute to carbon sequestration in soils but are limited by uncertainty due to data variability and specific implementation conditions.

Recommendations:

Address Data Gaps: Improving the accuracy and consistency of data is crucial for maximizing the effectiveness of these measures.

Optimize Land Use: Strategic land use optimization is essential to fully leverage the carbon sequestration potential of the identified measures.

Overall, the study highlights the significant potential for reducing agricultural greenhouse gas emissions through targeted C sequestration practices, emphasizing the need for enhanced data and optimized land use strategies. Further, it offers a framework allowing further refinement and implementation of such measures at both regional and national levels.

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Introduction

In order to estimate achievable organic carbon sequestration potentials for European agricultural soils, we need to know

- The area on which *additional* measures can be implemented that increase soil organic carbon (SOC) accrual, and
- How much C can be sequestered in that area.

In EJP SOIL-CarboSeq, we aimed to do this for individual agricultural measures that are well established and where SOC accrual is proven. Thus, only measures were considered that significantly increased SOC storage in European long-term field experiments by increasing either inputs of autochthonous carbon into the soil or its mean residence time in the soil (*Panagea et al., 2023*). As a result of the work conducted in WP3, organic amendments including compost, manure and sewage sludge were not further considered because neither composting nor fermentation increases the mean residence time of organic carbon on the long-term (WP3 Final report). Carbonized organic amendments, commonly referred to as biochar, were the only organic amendment type considered because of its long-term stability in the soil (*Wang et al., 2016*).

The following report is divided into three parts. In Part I, we introduce and define the selected SOC accrual measures for European agricultural soils. In Part II, a harmonized, general framework to define individual areas of implementation is presented and applied at a 10 x 10 km spatial resolution to all EU-27 and/or EJPSOIL member countries using open, pan-European datasets. The resulting areas of implementation feed into CarboSeq's Level II approach for estimating pan-European C sequestration potentials in soils (Figure 1) and are shown in part III.

The report is based on the results of three consortium-wide Online workshops held in October 2022 (see notes in annex), on follow-up discussions at the face-to-face project meetings in Rome in September 2022 and in Krakow in October 2023 and on bilateral exchanges with respective WP and task leaders.

All partners are invited to refine the application of the presented framework in their own countries and/or model regions, e.g. by including non-publicly available national data sources and/or data which is locally available at a higher spatial resolution (Level III approach). The individual implementation of the Level III approach to refine the area of application is optional as foreseen in the project proposal.

Figure 1. Approaches to estimate C sequestration potentials for European agricultural soils within the CarboSeq project.

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Part I – Overview of C accrual measures

Technical solutions

Tillage

Non-inversion tillage

Synonyms: reduced tillage; minimum tillage

Definition of the measure: farming system where soil is tilled (loosened) but not turned (inverted) throughout the entire crop rotation

Reference / control: inversion tillage (synonym: ploughing); regularly ploughed soil

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: soil water conservation (in arid and semi-arid regions); lower erosion risk; improved soil structure; reduced fuel and machinery costs; reduced working time; reduced soil disturbance benefits soil biota

Biophysical / environmental constraints : soil compaction; risk of weed infestation (competitor for light, nutrients and water); proliferation of certain pest and diseases

Technical constraints¹: crop establishment and development in very wet soils; conversion time, machinery costs and know-how to successfully implement no-tillage

Zero-tillage

Synonyms: no-tillage; direct drilling

Definition of the measure: farming system where soil is never tilled throughout the entire crop rotation; crops are sown directly into soil

Reference / control: inversion tillage (see non-inversion tillage above)

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: soil water conservation (in arid and semi-arid regions); lower erosion risk; higher nitrogen content; improved soil structure; reduced fuel and machinery costs; less working time; less soil disturbance benefits soil biota

Biophysical / environmental constraints: soil compaction (sometimes only first years); risk of weed infestation (competitor for light, nutrients and water); proliferation of certain pest and diseases; not very compatible with organic farming

Technical constraints: depends on crops grown and organic fertilisation (this determines the weight of the machinery and thus if tillage is needed to alleviate compaction; not feasible with root and tuber crops); crop establishment and development in very wet soils; conversion time, machinery costs and know-how to implement successful no-tillage; in irrigated crops, there are soils with surface sealing and hard pans that will be difficult to handle with zero tillage

Irrigation

Definition of the measure: the artificial watering of the land for the purpose of growing crops

¹ Case study on constraints for adopting non-inversion tillage: Bijttebier et al. (2018). Adoption of non-inversion tillage across Europe: Use of a behavioral approach in understanding decision making of farmers. Land use policy, 78, 460-471.

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Reference / control: rain-fed cropping

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: higher crop yield and yield stability; more options to diversify cropping systems; allows precision farming particularly in drip irrigation systems

Biophysical / environmental constraints: nitrogen leaching; decrease of biodiversity in soil and aboveground because as irrigation favors adoption of large monocultures and high-input farming systems; increased use of agrochemicals; potential soil degradation because of salinization / sodification

Technical constraints: water availability (quality and quantity); existence of irrigation infrastructure (storage, pumping, distribution); efficiency of the irrigation systems

Biochar

Synonyms: Pyrochar

Definition of the measure: application of pyrolysed organic material, commonly referred to as biochar, to the soil

Reference / control: agricultural land without biochar amendment

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: reduces odor emissions when added to slurry; soil bulk density reduction; increased biological activity; possible co-sequestration of SOC (negative priming); enhanced aggregate stability; reduction of nutrient leaching and N₂O emissions; improved water retention and water use efficiency depending on soil texture; acidic soil pH correction; increased root biomass

Biophysical / environmental constraints: none

Technical constraints: the production technique is fully developed, but the number of production units currently limit the amount of biochar that could be utilized and applied in agriculture. The availability of biomass for biochar production is another bottleneck for biochar production at large scale, as most organic wastes are currently recycled. The biomass availability for biochar production is also determined by biomass prices on the different markets, making a quantitative estimate difficult. Biochar production at large scale would therefore be in competition with existing circuits of organic by-product/waste valorisation/recycling.

Crop rotations

Perennial legumes and temporary ley management

Definition of the measure: introduction of perennial legumes and/or ley in rotation with annual crops

Reference / control: crop rotations without perennial legumes and/or ley

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: increases the number of vertical biopores; less mineral N fertilizer needed; good for soil health; biodiversity; soil protection (reduced erosion)

Biophysical / environmental constraints: depends on crop type

Technical constraints: none

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Cover crops

Synonyms: intermediate crop; catch crop

Definition of the measure: introduction of additional plant cover within existing cropping systems to cover temporarily bare soils, as in e.g. bare winter fallows

Reference / control: cropland with partially bare soil

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: attraction of insects; increased biodiversity; increased nitrogen availability / reduced nitrogen leaching; lower erosion risk; improved weed control; improved soil structure; increased attraction of the agricultural landscape

Biophysical / environmental constraints: growing season needs to be long enough; water effects for the following main crop are not yet fully elucidated

Technical constraints: none

Crop residues

Definition of the measure: leaving crop residues on the field, i.e., lower export of plant parts via harvest

Reference / control: removal of crop residues without return via organic amendments

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: improved soil structure; protection against runoff and sediment loss; increased and better nutrient availability; soil biodiversity

Biophysical / environmental constraints: depending on the needs of the chosen crop

Technical constraints: availability of suitable machinery; increase of weeds and plant pathogens that may increase pesticide usage

Woody vegetation

Hedgerows

Definition of the measure: additional planting of lines of woody vegetation, often forming a boundary or fence around land parcels; the woody vegetation often includes shrubs and small trees and is typically managed.

Reference / control: agricultural land without hedgerows

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: biodiversity (birds, macro fauna, corridors for migrating species); production of additional biomass (feed and fibre); risk of extreme micro-climate reduced (e.g., lower wind speed and evapo-transpiration lead to increased water storage in the soil); shadow and shelter for flora and fauna; reduced erosion, runoff and nutrient leaching

Biophysical / environmental constraints: possible competition for water and nutrients with main crop

Technical constraints: availability of planting material, especially for local species as required in some areas; machine park to manage the hedges

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Alley cropping

Definition of the measure: planting of individual trees on cropland in lines covering between 10-15% of the field. The trees are grown for more than 25 years before harvest (no short rotation coppices).

Reference / control: cropland without trees.

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: biodiversity (birds, macro fauna, corridors for migrating species); production of additional biomass (feed and fibre); risk of extreme micro-climate reduced (e.g. lower wind speed and evapo-transpiration lead to increased water storage in the soil); shadow and shelter for flora and fauna; reduced erosion, runoff and nutrient leaching

Biophysical / environmental constraints: regions with little sunshine where shading of trees has only negative effects

Technical constraints: possibly problematic with drainage systems; farmers may have to adapt with driving and machines to drive around trees

Silvopasture

Definition of the measure: conversion of grazed permanent grassland, commonly referred to as pasture, to silvopasture

Reference / control: pasture without silvopasture

Co-benefits beyond C accrual in soils: soil protection (less erosion); increased biodiversity at the farm scale; allowing animal grazing and the delivery of multiple ecosystem services (including animal welfare via shade)

Biophysical / environmental constraints: in pastures, animals will assemble under trees creating hotspots for N leaching, NH₃ and N₂O emissions, topsoil compaction

Technical constraints: grass and tree leaves might get mixed up reducing fodder quality

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Part II – Area of implementation

General Terminology

The EJP SOIL- CarboSeq project focuses on C sequestration potentials in mineral agricultural soils. In theory, if land use and management were optimized solely to maximize SOC stocks, all agricultural land with mineral soil could potentially sequester C. Therefore, within the project, we referred to this land as the *theoretical area of implementation*, A_{theory} . In a given region or pixel i , A_{theory} is defined as

$$A_{theory,i} = A_{land,i} * f_{agr,i} * (1 - f_{peat,i})$$

where $A_{land,i}$ is the land surface area of i in km², $f_{agr,i}$ is the land fraction of i used for agriculture including annual crops, permanent crops as well as managed grassland, and $f_{peat,i}$ denotes the fraction of agricultural land in i covered with organic soils. The two factors $f_{agr,i}$ and $f_{peat,i}$ can take values from 0 (= none of the land) to 1 (= all land).

The theoretical area of implementation is therefore defined as

$$A_{theory} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i}$$

where n denotes the number of regions or pixels considered.

To support CarboSeq's Level II approach (see Figure 1), A_{theory} was calculated for all the landmass of EU-27 countries and/or EJP SOIL member countries². This landmass was divided into $n = 55126$ pixels, each 10 km by 10 km in size. For each pixel i and management practice, individual areas of implementation were calculated. The factor $f_{agr,i}$ indicated presence (value = 1) or absence (value = 0) of agricultural land based on *Corine Land Cover* (2018) Class 2: Agricultural areas, including arable land, permanent crops, pastures and heterogeneous agricultural areas. The land proportion with organic soil $f_{peat,i}$ was derived from the peatland map by *Tubiello et al.* (2016). The Inspire conform ETRS-LAEA projection (EPSG:3035) served as the coordinate reference system.

Figure 2. Maps used to calculate the theoretical area of implementation (A_{theory}), from left to right: landmass (A_{land}), land fraction with agricultural land (f_{agr}), and land fraction with organic soil (f_{peat}).

² With the exception of the following NUTS regions FRY, ES70, PT20, PT30, NO0B, i.e. outermost regions as defined in Articles 349 and 355 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and the Norwegian islands Svalbard and Jan Mayen. National boundaries were defined according to Eurostat/GISCO (2023).

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In total, A_{theory} covered about 220 million hectares, with the highest proportion found in Turkey (15%), followed by France (14%), Spain (11%), Germany (8%), Poland (7%), Italy (7%), Romania (6%) and United Kingdom (5%). The other 23 countries together accounted for about a quarter of A_{theory} (Table 1).

In practice, a more feasible area of implementation represents only a fraction of A_{theory} . This fraction is affected by

- the intensity of which a given measure is already implemented in a given region, and
- biophysical / environmental as well as technical constraints, which hamper the further intensification of that measure in that region, and
- other constraints (e.g. economic, legal and social).

This report focuses on the intersection of theoretical, biophysical and technical areas of implementation of individual agricultural management practices that increase SOC accrual (Figure 3, diagonal stripes). If the implementation of a given measure would lead to extensification of farming or change in people/animal diets, such changes were kept minor and EU long-term policy goals were used as a rough guide to define feasible areas of implementation.

Figure 3. Venn diagram illustrating different areas of implementation for C accrual measures. While the theoretical area is the same for all measures (solid line), the biophysical and technical areas of implementation differ among individual measures (dashed line).

Technical solutions

Tillage

Non-inversion tillage

Within A_{theory} only land that is

- used for annual crops
- regularly ploughed

Here, in the entire crop rotation, any inversion tillage activity will be stopped completely and exclusively non-inversion tillage practices are implemented. Hence, the area of implementation for non-inversion tillage, $A_{non_inversion_till}$, was defined as

$$A_{non_inversion_till} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{arable,i} * f_{plough,i}$$

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where $f_{arable,i}$ indicated arable land (*Corine Land Cover*, 2018, class 21: arable land) as a fraction of total agricultural land (*Corine Land Cover*, 2018, class 2: agricultural areas) in i , and $f_{plough,i}$ was the fraction of arable land with ploughing in i . Data for f_{plough} originated from Farm Structure Surveys carried out by EU Member States, as published by *EUROSTAT* (2020a) at NUTS2 level. If in a given NUTS2 region, values for f_{plough} were available for several years, we used the respective multi-annual average values. Gaps in the tillage data from *EUROSTAT* (2020a) were filled with multi-annual average values from *FAOSTAT* (2023) at the country level, and, finally with the global gridded tillage layer by *Porwollik et al.* (2019). It is important to note that for Norway, Sweden and Finland no SOC accrual is anticipated due to the climatic conditions (*Kätterer et al.*, 2012; *Budai et al.*, 2024), thus in Part III of this document their emission factor is set to 1.00.

Figure 4. Area of implementation for non-inversion tillage.

Zero-tillage

Within A_{theory} , only land that is

- used for annual crops
- regularly ploughed
- farmed conventionally (= not organically)

Here, in the entire crop rotation, any tillage activity is stopped completely. Hence, the area of implementation for zero-tillage, A_{zero_till} , was defined as

$$A_{zero_till} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{arable,i} * f_{plough,i} * (1 - f_{organic,i})$$

where $f_{organic,i}$ indicated arable land with organic farming as a fraction of total arable land based on *EUROSTAT* (2023) data on NUTS2 level gap-filled with *FAOSTAT* (2023) data on the country level. It is important to note that for Norway, Sweden and Finland no SOC accrual is anticipated due to the climatic conditions (*Kätterer et al.*, 2012; *Budai et al.*, 2024), thus in Part III of this document their emission factor is set to 1.00.

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Figure 5. Area of implementation for zero-tillage.

Irrigation

Within A_{theory} , only land that is

- not irrigated permanently, but
- equipped with infrastructure for permanent irrigation

Here, sufficient irrigation of any crop in any year to avoid water-deficits. Hence, the area of implementation for irrigation, $A_{irrigation}$, was defined as

$$A_{irrigation} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * (f_{irrigable,i} - f_{irrigated,i})$$

Where for each pixel i , $f_{irrigable,i}$ indicated the fraction of land with infrastructure for irrigation and $f_{irrigated,i}$ the fraction of land that was already irrigated, both based on the “Global Map of Irrigation Areas” by Siebert et al. (2013).

Figure 6. Area of implementation for irrigation.

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Biochar

Within A_{theory} , only land

- that is cropland (annuals and perennials)
- that has a soil with a pH value of 7 or less avoiding effects of over alkalization as biochar raises the pH level (*He et al., 2021; Jeffery et al., 2017*)

Here, over multiple years, apply a cumulative sum of up to 50 t ha⁻¹ of biochar and not more to avoid over alkalization and linked crop productivity losses (*Jeffery et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2013*). Hence, the area of implementation for biochar amendments, $A_{biochar}$, was defined as

$$A_{irrigation} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * (f_{arable,i} + f_{perennial,i}) * f_{pH}$$

where $f_{perennial,i}$ indicated agricultural land with permanent crops (*Corine Land Cover, 2018, class 22: perennial crops*) as a fraction of total agricultural land (*Corine Land Cover, 2018, class 2: agricultural areas*). The factor f_{pH} indicated presence (value = 1) or absence (value = 0) of acidic to neutral soil with pH values measured in water lower than 7 based on SoilGrids 2.0 data (*Poggio et al., 2021*).

Figure 7. Area of implementation for biochar amendments.

Crop rotations

Perennial legumes and temporary ley management

Within A_{theory} , only land

- that is currently used for green maize³

Here, replace all green maize with perennial legumes and/or temporary ley management. Hence, the area of implementation, A_{fodder} , was defined as

³ We adopt the following definition from EUROSTAT: “This includes green maize directly consumed by animals (without silage) and whole cobs (grain, rachis, husk) harvested for feedstuff or silage, as well as for renewable energy production. Maize harvested as grain and corn-cob-mix is excluded.”

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$$A_{fodder} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{arable,i} * f_{green_maize,i}$$

where f_{green_maize} indicated land with green maize as a fraction of total arable land based on NUTS2 level data from *EUROSTAT* (2020b) and *EUROSTAT* (2024b), gap filled with *EUROSTAT* (2024a) for Turkey.

Figure 8. Area of implementation for perennial legumes and temporary ley management.

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Cover crops

Within A_{theory} , only land that is

- partially bare in time (bare winter fallows in annual crop rotations) and
- where the introduction of additional plant cover is biophysically possible without irrigation

Here, covers all bare soil with cover crops.

The analyses were restricted to bare winter fallows in annual crop rotations as there is no pan-European data on bare soil between rows of permanent crops and thus the area of implementation for cover crops A_{cc} , is defined as follows

$$A_{cc} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{rainfed_arable,i} * f_{bare,i} * f_{climate,i}$$

where $f_{rainfed_arable,i}$ indicated rainfed arable land (*Corine Land Cover*, 2018, class 21: arable land) as a fraction of total agricultural land (*Corine Land Cover*, 2018, class 2: agricultural areas). The factor $f_{bare,i}$ indicated arable land with bare winter fallows as a fraction of total arable land based on *EUROSTAT* (2020c), gap filled with data from *BFS* (2017) for Switzerland and the European mean of 0.27 for Norway and Turkey. The factor $f_{climate,i}$ indicated whether the climatic conditions would allow to grow cover crops (value = 1) or not (value = 0). The latter was implemented as outlined by *Vanwindekens et al.* (2022). In brief, it was assumed that

- Cover crops are grown after a primary crop
- The primary crop needs a temperature sum after the 1th of January of 2440°C to maturity (*Holzämper et al.*, 2015)
- Cover crops need an average daily temperature of at least 5°C to grow
- Cover crops need a positive daily water balance to grow
- Cover crops need at least one month to establish before the 31th of December (*LfL*, 2011)

Climate data originated from *CHELSA* (*Brun et al.*, 2022).

Figure 9. Input parameters for calculation the area of implementation for cover crops. Left: Arable land with bare soil cover during winter. Right: Regions where climate allows cover crop cultivation during winter ($f_{climate,i}$).

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Figure 10. Area of implementation for cover crops.

Crop residue management

Within A_{theory} , only land

- with open fires

Here, in future, prevent the re-occurrence of any fire activity. Considering the availability of European fire activity data, the area of implementation for optimized crop residue management, $A_{residue}$, was defined as

$$A_{residue} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{arable,i} * f_{fire,i}$$

Where for each pixel i , f_{fire} indicated presence (value = 1) or absence (value = 0) of open crop residue burning between 1997 and 2015 according to the Global Fire Emission Database (Randerson et al., 2017). Pixels with multi-annual mean carbon emissions from open crop residue burning lower than $5 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ were classified as unburnt.

Figure 11. Area of implementation for improved crop residue management.

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Woody vegetation

The European Commission has defined the mid-term goal to “bring back at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity features” (COM, 2020). These high-diversity landscape features include woody features as well as grassy, wet (e.g., ponds) and stony elements(e.g., stone walls). Today, only two EU countries have reached the 10% target already – these are Malta and Cyprus (Figure 12). All other EU countries are still below the 10% target. Woody features, including hedgerows, rows of trees (as in alley cropping systems) and single trees (as in silvopastoral systems), are currently more dominant in agricultural grasslands than in arable land (Figure 13). Thus, the C accrual measures hedges, alley cropping and silvopasture will be combined into one measure called woody vegetation.

Figure 12. Present share of agricultural land covered with high-diversity landscape features by country based on data from the LUCAS 2022 field survey (D’Andrimont et al., 2023) and EUROSTAT (2023a). The Commission’s biodiversity target is indicated with a dashed horizontal line.

Figure 13. Current area extent of woody features on arable land (left) and other agricultural land including grassland and perennial crops (right). Pixels in the respective agricultural land class but without data on woody features are shown in dark grey.

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In the CarboSeq project, we used the Commission's biodiversity target as the basis for defining implementation areas for additional woody vegetation in the agricultural landscape. Specifically, we defined the following two scenarios to achieve the Commission's biodiversity target at the country level.

Ambitious scenario: Only woody features on arable land increase

In the ambitious scenario, we assume that the 10% landscape feature target is met by increasing only woody features on arable land. The extent of woody features on grassland as well as the extents of other landscape features is kept constant in this scenario (Figure 14).

Hence, in the ambitious scenario, the area of implementation for additional woody vegetation in the agricultural landscape, $A_{wood_ambitious}$, was defined as

$$A_{wood_ambitious} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{arable,i} * f_{A,i}$$

where $f_{A,i}$ is the area of additional woody vegetation as a fraction of total arable land in i . This fraction was calculated as follows

$$f_{A,i} = \frac{0.1 * A_{agr,j} - f_{lf_today,j} * A_{agr,j}}{A_{arable,j}}$$

where $A_{agr,j}$ is the total agricultural land area in country j based on *EUROSTAT* (2023a), A_{arable} is the arable land area and f_{lf_today} is the fraction of total agricultural land covered with high-diversity landscape features today according to *D'Andrimont et al. (2023)*. Missing values for $f_{A,i}$ in Turkey, Switzerland, UK and Norway were gap-filled with the European mean value of 0.063.

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Figure 14. In the ambitious scenario, only woody features on arable land (brown bars) are increased to reach the 10% target on a national level.

Figure 15. Area of implementation for additional woody features (ambitious scenario)

Conservative scenario: All landscape features increase by a constant, country-specific factor
 In the conservative scenario, we assume that the 10% landscape feature target is met by increasing all landscape features the same, country-specific factor. In this scenario, all landscape features are assumed to increase by the same factor (Figure 16).

Hence, for the conservative scenario, the area of implementation for additional woody vegetation in the agricultural landscape, A_{wood_cons} , was defined as

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$$A_{wood_cons} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{B,i}$$

where $f_{B,i}$ is the area of additional woody vegetation as a fraction of total agricultural land in i . This fraction was calculated as follows

$$f_{B,i} = \frac{0.10}{f_{lf_today,j}} * f_{wf_today,j} - f_{wf_today,j}$$

where $f_{wf_today,j}$ is today's woody feature area as a fraction of total agricultural land area according to D'Andrimont et al. (2023). Missing values for $f_{B,i}$ in Turkey, Switzerland, UK and Norway were gap-filled with the European mean value of 0.022.

Figure 16. In the conservative scenario, all landscape features (brown, green and grey bars) are increased by a constant, country-specific factor to reach the 10% target on a national level.

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Figure 17. Area of implementation for additional woody features (conservative scenario)

Part II - Synthesis

The potential area for implementing additional C accrual measures is considerably higher in cropland than grassland – potential C sequestration in grassland is restricted to the plantation of additional woody features like hedgerows and individual trees. In cropland, the largest areas of implementation are available for technical solutions (tillage > biochar > irrigation) and improved crop rotations (cover crops > crop residues > perennial legumes, temporary ley), while the area available for additional woody features is relatively small (Figure 18). Table 1 shows country-specific areas of implementation for individual SOC accrual measures.

Figure 18. Carbon accrual measures ranked by total area of implementation in million hectares.

The estimated area of implementation for C sequestration measures in European agriculture specifically aims at providing feasible potentials that are technically possible and not restricted by biophysical constraints. This is different to previous estimates. For some measures such as agroforestry/hedgerows it was not possible to constraint their potential via technical and biophysical limits. However, in order to ensure feasibility of the estimated area we considered also political targets (e.g. the EU biodiversity strategy for hedgerows). Thus, the reported areas of implementation are not independent of socio-economic and political considerations since agriculture needs to transform in such a way that multiple targets are achieved including the target to create C sinks for climate change mitigation.

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Table 1. Total areas of implementation ranked by potential carbon accrual measure and country in thousand hectares.

Country	Theoretical	Technical solutions			Crop rotations			Woody vegetation		
		Tillage		Biochar	Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop residues	Perennial legumes, temporary ley	Ambitious estimate	Conservative estimate
		Reduced	Zero							
Austria	2569	792	662	677	74	130	0	77	140	46
Belgium	1709	522	510	448	29	114	0	122	45	27
Bulgaria	5544	1786	1766	2057	650	1513	2936	28	194	102
Croatia	2178	568	549	415	3	322	248	21	33	21
Cyprus	411	95	93	0	11	11	0	1	0	0
Czechia	4443	1845	1665	1843	66	384	0	254	216	88
Denmark	2797	2061	1912	1763	319	39	0	183	121	56
Estonia	881	201	172	192	1	0	0	4	26	11
Finland	2278	834	763	436	92	0	0	0	34	5
France	30711	7166	6938	9506	1149	2694	46	1035	824	549
Germany	16854	6824	6434	7572	351	2174	0	1906	733	256
Greece	4684	1575	1526	190	393	283	673	27	155	43
Hungary	5432	3716	3611	1159	256	1471	384	79	302	143
Ireland	3793	255	253	244	0	7	0	6	29	58
Italy	15201	6505	5936	1366	1419	1164	1632	298	280	117
Latvia	2195	793	718	507	1	53	2	16	87	35
Lithuania	3253	1602	1518	1257	4	573	23	22	162	63
Luxembourg	136	26	25	27	0	5	0	11	6	3
Malta	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	1568	365	354	294	273	101	0	75	27	9
Norway	1346	172	163	165	121	6	0	0	30	6
Poland	16206	10287	10048	8268	127	1924	17	549	1004	368
Portugal	4216	392	380	1081	405	68	47	54	39	15
Romania	13333	6701	6644	4806	2178	1930	3151	38	841	474
Slovakia	2310	1094	1011	668	246	483	25	94	133	48
Slovenia	685	102	94	87	22	16	0	17	13	9
Spain	23922	9192	8900	1612	905	1259	922	65	1201	243
Sweden	3504	2079	1781	1152	138	28	0	16	61	13
Switzerland	811	316	285	215	29	111	0	46	24	8
Turkey	33694	16502	16304	3343	4029	2201	1447	230	1164	459
United Kingdom	11551	3410	3332	4759	104	493	44	185	369	190
TOTAL	218226	87778	84347	56109	13395	19557	11597	5459	8293	3465

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Part III – Calculation of the C sequestration potential of agricultural measures

How to calculate the C sequestration potential of a measure?

In work package 2 of the CarboSeq project, emission factors derived from data from European long-term field experiments and other published European data (Panagea et al., 2023) considering pedoclimatic and management factors for each measure (Table 2). These emission factors have been used to calculate the Tier 2 C sequestration potential for European agricultural land as follows

$$C_{seq,j} = C_{stock_{pot,j}} - C_{stock_{ref,j}}$$

where $C_{seq,j}$ is the C sequestration potential for measure j (Mg C), $C_{stock_{pot}}$ is the potential long-term SOC stock within the area of application of measure j (Mg C), and $C_{stock_{ref}}$ is the current reference SOC stock without application of measure j (Mg C). The latter was calculated for measure j in i as follows

$$C_{stock_{ref,i,j}} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{theory,i} * f_{i,j} * C_{stock_{today,i}}$$

where $A_{theory,i}$ is the theoretical area of implementation in i (ha), $f_{i,j}$ is the fraction of the theoretical area of implementation for measure j in i and $C_{stock_{ref,i}}$ is the topsoil SOC stock in 0-30 cm depth in i derived from SoilGrids data (Mg ha⁻¹) (Poggio et al., 2021). The potential future SOC stock after implementing measure j in i was calculated as

$$C_{stock_{pot,i,j}} = C_{stock_{ref,i,j}} * EF_{i,j}$$

where $EF_{i,j}$ is the emission factor of measure j in region i.

The *Emission Factor* is the measure specific factor or calculation taken from Table 2 and $C_{stock_{ref}}$ is the SOC stock under current management conditions (Mg C ha⁻¹).

Table 2: Overview of the carbon (C) accrual measures, their area of implementation and their emission factors. ¹Value taken from (Kätterer et al., 2012) ²Value taken from (Leifeld et al., 2024) ³Value taken from (Emde et al., 2021) due to lack of sufficient European data. ⁴Value taken from (Drexler et al., 2021)

Agricultural measure	Pot. Area of implementation in 1000 ha	Emission factor
Reduced tillage	87778	In Norway, Sweden and Finland, 1.0 ¹ ; elsewhere based on equivalent soil mass approach: 1.03
Zero tillage	84347	In Norway, Sweden and Finland, 1.0 ¹ ; elsewhere based on equivalent soil mass approach: 1.11
Biochar	56109	Independent of SOC stock. Application rate 50 Mg ha ⁻¹ Calculation: Area of implementation * 37.40790106 Mg Biochar-C ²
Irrigation	13395	1.059 ³
Cover crops	19557	1.06
Crop residues	11597	1.114560 – 0.75746 * SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) + 0.214673 * cereals in rotation (%) + 0.002988 * clay content (%) - 0.000147 * annual rainfall (mm)
Perennial legumes, temporary ley	5459	1.182198 + 0.003957 * percentage difference of legumes in the rotation (%) - 0.129105 * SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
Woody vegetation (conservative)	3465	for cropland soil under hedges and alley cropping: 1.26
Woody vegetation (ambitious)	8293	To account for biomass, add 87 Mg C per implemented hectare ⁴

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The *C seq. pot. of a measure* has been converted into Mio t CO₂eq using the following equation:

$$1 \text{ CO}_2\text{eq} = 1 \text{ Mg C} * 3.67$$

To calculate the yearly potential carbon sequestration rates of agricultural measures, it is important to consider both the time period and the fact that agricultural practices do not indefinitely increase soil SOC (Don et al., 2024). This has been taken into account for each measure individually (Table 3) but assuming for soils that a new SOC equilibrium is reached in 50 years. This is a simplification since its dependence on climate and soil conditions and further, due to climate change equilibriums may never be reached. C accrual is mostly non-linear with highest C accrual rates in the first years while most of the C accrual is within 50 years after implementation of a measure (Johnston et al. 2009).

Table 3: Overview of carbon (C) accrual measures and the individual calculations to reach yearly C sequestration potential rates in carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂eq).

Agricultural measure	Calculation	Assumptions	Source
Reduced tillage	Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	Johnston et al., 2009
Zero tillage			
Biochar	Biochar-C content * F _{perm}	ECB certified Biochar C content after 100 years 1 Mg Biochar contains 0.81 Mg of C F _{perm} = 0.92	Leifeld et al., 2024 Hagemann et al., 2024
Irrigation	Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	Johnston et al., 2009
Cover crops	Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	Johnston et al., 2009
Crop residues	Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	Johnston et al., 2009
Perennial legumes, temporary ley	Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	Johnston et al., 2009
Woody vegetation (conservative)	For SOC: Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 50	SOC in equilibrium after 50 years	For soil: Johnston et al., 2009 For biomass: Drexler et al., 2021
Woody vegetation (ambitious)	For biomass: Total C sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq) / 30	Equilibrium biomass after 30 years	

Results of the Tier 2 approach of C sequestration potentials on European scale

The results of the calculation showed that on European scale biochar application has by far the highest potential to increase C followed by woody features, tillage practices and only small total potentials with measures affecting crop rotations both in total amounts (Figure 19) as well as in yearly C sequestration potentials (Table 4).

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Figure 19: Carbon accrual measures ranked by total carbon sequestration potential in million Mg CO₂eq.

Table 4: Overview of the selected carbon (C) accrual measures and their C sequestration potential

Agricultural measure	Total carbon sequestration potential (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq)	Yearly pot. carbon sequestration rate (Mio Mg CO ₂ eq a ⁻¹)	Considered time (years)
Reduced tillage	446	8.9	50
Zero tillage	1574	31.5	50
Biochar	7703	77.0	100
Irrigation	140	2.8	50
Cover crops	208	4.1	50
Crop residues	437	8.7	50
Perennial legumes, temporary ley	361	7.2	50
Woody vegetation (conservative)	97 (SOC) 1106 (Biomass) 1203 (total)	1.9 (SOC) 36.8 (Biomass) 38.8 (total)	SOC: 50 Biomass: 30
Woody vegetation (ambitious)	380 (SOC) 2647 (Biomass) 3027 (total)	7.6 (SOC) 88.2 (Biomass) 95.8 (total)	
Total conservative (not considering zero tillage)	10847	147.7	
Total ambitious (not considering reduced tillage)	13998	204.7	

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Table 5: Total carbon sequestration potential ranked by measure and country in Mio Mg CO₂eq.

Country	Technical solutions			Crop rotations			Woody vegetation		
	Tillage		Biochar	Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop residues	Perennial legumes, temporary ley	Ambitious estimate	Conservative estimate
	Reduced	Zero							
Austria	5	15	93	1	2	0	5	52	16
Belgium	3	11	61	< 1	1	0	8	17	9
Bulgaria	9	32	282	6	15	114	2	70	36
Croatia	3	12	57	< 1	4	8	1	12	7
Cyprus	< 1	1	0	< 1	< 1	0	< 1	< 1	< 1
Czechia	10	34	253	1	4	0	17	79	31
Denmark	13	44	242	4	< 1	0	13	45	20
Estonia	2	5	26	< 1	0	0	< 1	10	4
Finland	0	0	60	2	0	0	0	14	2
France	40	141	1305	12	30	1	70	303	188
Germany	42	144	1040	4	27	0	129	272	91
Greece	7	24	26	4	2	22	2	56	14
Hungary	20	72	159	3	16	16	5	111	51
Ireland	2	8	33	0	< 1	0	< 1	11	19
Italy	34	114	188	15	13	57	19	102	40
Latvia	6	19	70	< 1	1	< 1	1	33	12
Lithuania	10	33	173	< 1	7	1	1	60	22
Luxembourg	< 1	1	4	0	< 1	0	1	2	1
Malta	< 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	2	8	40	4	1	0	5	10	3
Norway	0	0	23	2	< 1	0	0	12	2
Poland	48	170	1135	1	19	1	33	361	129
Portugal	2	7	148	5	1	1	4	14	5
Romania	32	115	660	19	18	130	2	303	165
Slovakia	6	21	92	3	6	1	6	49	17
Slovenia	1	2	12	< 1	< 1	0	1	5	3
Spain	37	132	221	8	10	30	4	425	82
Sweden	0	0	158	2	< 1	0	1	24	5
Switzerland	3	9	30	< 1	2	0	3	9	3
Turkey	84	303	459	42	22	54	15	423	159
United Kingdom	27	96	653	2	7	1	13	143	67
TOTAL	448	1573	7703	140	208	437	361	3027	1203

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Evaluation of the Tier 2 European C sequestration potentials of measures

The results of the Tier 2 approach of C sequestration potential on European scale clearly demonstrates the varying effectiveness of different C accrual measures. Overall, our conservative estimated C sequestration potential of 147.7 million Mg CO₂eq per year could reduce or compensate up to 32% of the current greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from European agriculture, including Norway, Switzerland, and Turkey (467.2 million Mg CO₂eq in 2020 (Statista Search Department, 2024a; FOEN, 2024; Statista Search Department, 2024b, 2024c, respectively). Rodrigues et al. (2021) estimated a comparable or slightly lower potential compensation of 0.1-27% of GHG emissions from the agricultural sector on national scale across 13 EU member states through various C accrual measures. Additionally, Lugato et al. (2014) estimated that a subset of measures (reduced tillage, crop residue management, ley rotations, and cover crops) could reduce GHG emissions by in total 549-2141 Mt CO₂eq by 2100. This aligns with the values of total potential C sequestration effects estimated here for the same subset of measures with 1452 Mt CO₂eq over a time period of 50 years.

In addition to increasing SOC, each C accrual measure has its own synergies and trade-offs. These aspects are discussed in a broad overview in Part I of this document. However, we want to highlight in more detail the limitations of the emission factors and the estimation of the area of implementation.

Reduced tillage

The IPCC suggests that reduced tillage may lead to an increase in SOC with a EFs ranging from 0.98 to 1.05 for boreal, cool and warm temperate regions (IPCC et al., 2019). This factor is a simplification and is on small scale influenced by variables such as climate, soil type and crop type (IPCC, 2019) yet it falls in line with our new European EF of 1.03. The impact on N₂O emissions, however, is less straightforward, as reduced tillage can sometimes lead to either increases or decreases in N₂O emissions depending on soil conditions and other management practices (Guenet et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023). In Carboseq WP5 this topic is further elucidated.

By only considering European long-term field experiments (LTEs), we found no significant differences in EFs across Europe based on pedo-climatic conditions leading to a single European EF for reduced tillage of 1.05 (Panagea et al., 2023). However, for dry boreal and temperate climates the IPCC expects losses of SOC with EFs of 0.98 and 0.99 (IPCC, 2019), respectively which is in contrast with our findings. This may lead to an overestimation of C accrual from this measure especially for the northern countries Norway, Sweden and Finland. To avoid this overestimation we set the EFs to 1.00 of these countries which affected 3.5 % of the total area of implementation following the findings of Kätterer et al. (2012) and Budai et al. (2024) stating that due to pedo-climatic conditions changes in tillage management will have no significant effect on SOC stocks, yet other positive effects can occur, such as economic benefits. Finally, due to the availability of data, the EF has been calculated based on the top 30 cm of soil and does not include the whole soil profile which may lead to an overestimation of the EF and the linked C sequestration potential as effects on subsoil are neglected and C may actually just be redistributed (Haddaway et al., 2017).

No tillage

The IPCC suggests that no tillage always leads to an increase in SOC with a EFs ranging from 1.03 to 1.10 for boreal, cool and warm temperate regions, respectively (IPCC, 2019) and is as reduced tillage influenced by pedo-climatic conditions, crop types and may also affect other GHG emissions (IPCC, 2019). The new European wide EF of 1.11 from this study based solely on European LTEs is

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comparably high and was surprisingly not affected by pedo-climatic conditions. This may be linked to limitations and a bias in the LTE dataset, with unequal representation of all climates. 14 out of 27 zero-tillage experiments in our dataset were conducted in Mediterranean climate with the majority located in semiarid Spain (Panagea et al., 2023). Further, Kätterer et al. (2012) and Budai et al. (2024) found no or negative effects on SOC for Sweden, Finland and Norway respectively, and thus, these areas have been assigned an EF of 1.00 similar to the reduced tillage measure, reducing the total area of implementation by 3.2 %. We want to stress that other positive effects can occur, such as economic benefits. Finally, due to the availability of data, the EF has been calculated based on the top 30 cm of soil and does not include the whole soil profile which may lead to an overestimation of the EF and the linked C sequestration potential as effects on subsoil are neglected and C may actually just be redistributed (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2021).

Biochar

Biochar is by far the most efficient measure to increase SOC that was identified in this study which is linked to the large area of implementation and the fact that it degrades very slowly (Leifeld et al., 2024). Pyrolysis of biomass is a promising processing method to stabilize C (Wang et al., 2016) that can be added to soils as amendment in order to improve soil properties. For our analysis, only studies were considered that are in line with the requirements of the European Biochar Certificate (EBC, 2012) and of the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2088 on pyrolysis and gasification materials (European Union, 2021). The used calculation for potential C sequestration through biochar takes into account i) C losses from the initial processing (pyrolysis) and ii) a calculated time-horizon of 100 years, following the F_{perm} concept of (IPCC, 2019). Here, the area of implementation is only limited by soil pH to avoid over-alkalization through biochar application in alkaline soils which may cause to yield losses (Jeffery et al., 2017; He et al., 2021). Further, no more than 50 Mg biochar per hectare should be applied as also here, yield losses may occur (Jeffery et al., 2017). Beyond this application rate for agricultural soils in the temperate zone, we expect potential negative effects due to the liming effect of biochar and other impacts. Moreover, benefits of biochar for soil health, such as improved water infiltration capacity, water holding capacity, decreased soil bulk density, improved nutrient availability and more (Schmidt et al., 2021), are expected mainly in semi-arid regions and less in temperate regions. No yield effects have been found e.g. in climate regions with a mean annual temperature $<9^{\circ}\text{C}$. The key issue with this measure is linked to biomass availability as feedstock for biochar and the production capacity. Currently, the current ECB certified production of biochar in 27 EU-member states, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland is 64106 t of biochar per year (Hagemann et al., 2024). At this rate, the production of the needed biochar amounts to fully use the potential of this measure would take approx. 43,750 years. Thus, this measure becomes only impactful if more production units are built, which in turn requires additional biomass to produce the biochar. One possibility may be the use of biomass that is currently hardly used e.g., 146 Mio tons of straw biomass produced in the EU annually (Monforti et al., 2015) could be converted to 32 Mio tons biochar per year if sufficient production units exist. Hedge prunings could also be used where 14 Mio tons of woody biomass are produced every year (Dyjakon and García-Galindo, 2019) that equal 3 Mio tons biochar per year. In addition, if the here suggested conservative woody vegetation measure would be fully implemented, up to 37 Mio tons of woody biomass could be produced and pyrolyzed into 8 Mio tons biochar per year. As an example, taking these three biomass sources together, assuming that sufficient production units exist, 68 years would be needed to produce the maximum potential biochar amount suggested for this measure to be applied to agricultural soils in Europe.

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Irrigation

This measure has some limitations while at the same time being ranked at the very bottom of all measures that foster SOC accrual. A new robust EF could not be derived as only three European experiments of sufficient quality could be identified in the work of WP2. For this, more field experiments are needed and until then have to make use of the EF of 1.059 as suggested by Emde et al. (2021) determined through a global meta-analysis. However, the irrigation method influences the effect on SOC and only sprinkler irrigation leads to SOC accrual according to Emde et al. (2021) meaning that the here presented C sequestration potential is only possible if all irrigation systems would be sprinkler systems which is unrealistic and moreover inefficient in terms of water consumption. We restricted the area of implementation to croplands with existing irrigation infrastructure assuming a certain amount of water being available with the infrastructure. However, due to climate change the water availability for agricultural irrigation purposes will be increasingly limited and requests to optimize water use in agriculture for maintaining and enhancing yield are in the focus while C sequestration in soils may remain simply as a side product.

Cover crops

The new European EFs for cover crops from our study correspond well with existing literature (Poeplau and Don, 2015), despite a lack of representative data from long-term field experiments from all climatic regions. Especially, experimental data from boreal and Mediterranean regions is underrepresented while at the same time long-term effects (>20 years) remain unknown as the average experimental duration was 11 years (Panagea et al., 2023). Experiments need to be continued long-term and new field trials need to be set up in the underrepresented regions in order to better elucidate the effects of cover cropping on SOC accrual.

Further, the area of implementation can be improved if more data is available on crop rotations, harvest and seeding times of main crops as this determines the extent to which cover crops can be sown and how long they can remain in the field. These two factors have a significant influence on the C input of cover crops to the soil (Gselman and Kramberger, 2008). Another critical assumption is that we assumed that cover crops are grown after non-irrigated winter wheat and thus neglecting any other crops on which cover crops may follow (Heller et al., 2024). Thus, differences in harvest time of different crops cannot be considered due to missing data on crop rotations and harvesting times at European scale, despite being most relevant for the growth and thus C input of the cover crops.

Crop residues

The new European EF of our study used for this measure is based on cereal straw and thus highly relevant yet, many other crop residues will not be well represented by this EF (Panagea et al., 2023). Only if additional crop residues can be left on the soil compared to current practice (including straw residue harvest and returning them to soils as part of farm yard manure) C sequestration in soils is possible. Thus, as for the area of implementation, only soils where currently crop residues are burned is considered. Changes of crop rotations or management practices towards increased residues left on the field are not considered as there is a lack of available field site specific data on current European wide crop rotations and management practices.

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Perennial legumes and temporary ley rotations

The option to increase the share of legumes in crop rotations was chosen as measure due to the strong base of available data from long-term experiments (LTEs) that cover the majority of pedoclimatic conditions in Europe. Additionally, the potential to enhance SOC stocks through this measure aligns with the current priorities on the political agenda of the European Union (European Commission, 2020). In Europe, legumes are grown on only 3% of arable land, yet they account for 30% of the EU's crop protein consumption (Häusling, 2011). To reduce the resulting import dependency, Europe is investing in boosting and reintroducing high-protein crops by "fostering EU-grown plant proteins" (European Commission, 2018, 2020). The data analysis showed that only forage legumes increase SOC (Panagea et al., 2023). Thus, through an increased share of forage legumes SOC accrual is possible in addition to multiple other soil health benefits such as reduction of N fertilization demand and reduced tillage needs (Kremen et al., 2012; Wezel et al., 2014; Garbach et al., 2017; Beillouin et al., 2019; Tamburini et al., 2020; Di Bene et al., 2022). The new European EF from our study applied here is a simplified version based on 21 LTEs across Europe. A regression equation per climatic zone was not performing well and was biased due to imbalanced data across the climatic zones. Thus, more experiments need to be established in the Atlantic, Boreal and Mediterranean climatic zones to improve EFs per climatic zone.

Defining the area of implementation for this measure was challenging since it could be applied to all arable land across Europe. A better approach towards a more feasible potential area of implementation involves creating a scenario where land use is optimized. Fodder legumes require animal production in order to use these crops. Enhancing the fodder production in Europe while at the same time enhancing animal production in Europe cannot be the political aim given the high share of agricultural GHG emissions being related to animal production (Leip et al., 2010).

Green maize (silage maize), used for energy production or animal fodder, is inappropriate for the human diet. Energy can be produced e.g., four times more efficiently through solar power when taking GHG emissions and energy output into account while at the same time soil erosion is decreased by 20-fold (Graebig et al., 2010). Furthermore, arable land currently used to grow green maize for fodder could be repurposed for more human diet food crops, doubling the food production efficiency (Van Zanten et al., 2016). The resulting decrease in fodder production could lead to a reduction in animal numbers further reducing GHG emission linked to livestock production (Van Zanten et al., 2016). Besides, for fodder production, replacing green maize with fodder legumes (e.g., alfalfa) or temporary ley would result in extensification, as less fodder per hectare would be grown (Lehtilä et al., 2024). However, this aligns with declining livestock numbers (EUROSTAT, 2023b) and the rise in vegetarian and vegan diets reducing the need for fodder. Thus, all areas currently used for green maize production were repurposed to introduce leguminous fodder crops with this measure into the crop rotation. Notably, substituting imported legumes with locally grown ones would provide an additional climate change mitigation benefit. This scenario represents just one of many possible variations for introducing this measure into a crop rotation.

Woody vegetation

Agroforestry systems are championed to store C in biomass and soil and therefore can become an active C sink in Europe if they are newly implemented (Drexler et al., 2021). This is reflected in the measure having the second highest potential of all identified measures to increase C stocks when considering SOC and C stored in aboveground biomass. Further, multiple synergy effects besides C

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accrual arise as mentioned in part I of this work. The new European EF for SOC is valid for hedgerows and alley cropping systems alike and represents the soil covered with woody vegetation and comes with the limitation that most data derive from Western Europe and thus applicability in other areas remains to be tested. The EF cannot be applied on soils under silvopasture and grassland management as the SOC is expected not to increase if grasslands are the reference system (Panagea et al., 2023).

The area used for this measure is also storing additional C in the aboveground biomass in the long-term. Therefore, it is consequent to include this C in the C sequestration potential of the measure. In agroforestry systems are many variables controlling C storage in biomass e.g. tree species, tree density, and percentage of trees included in hedges. All these variables can lead to varying C sequestration potentials. We follow the results of Drexler et al. (2021) for aboveground biomass suggesting an average C storage potential of hedge rows representative of the temperate climate zone, as this is currently the most comprehensive and representative study on this topic. Thus, this measure has the same belowground SOC effect on cropland soils under hedges and alley cropping management while for silvopasture and grasslands we assume no SOC effect. Subsequently, the aboveground C storage is based on hedges which are less diverse than tree species used in alley-cropping and silvopasture (Drexler et al., 2021).

To implement this measure, a scenario was designed in line with the European Commission's biodiversity strategy to increase the share of high-diversity features in the agricultural landscape to 10% aerial coverage (European Commission, 2020) as outlined in part II of this document. In practice, even the conservative variant of the measure is very ambitious, as we assume that farmers will plant hedges instead of easier and cheaper to implement landscape features such as buffer strips or rotational fallow land.

Synthesis part III

We showed that C sequestration could potentially compensate a relevant fraction of unavoidable GHG emissions from agriculture in Europe for a limited period of time of several decades. Different measures are in place that are well tested and often already part of agriculture practice. Fostering and enlarging the area of implementation of these measures could thus contribute to climate mitigation. More important, all of these measures have positive synergistic effects on different environmental targets such as soil health and biodiversity. The measure with the highest potential for C sequestration, biochar application, is different to all other measures since its degree of implementation in European agriculture is actually very low with only very few pyrolysis plants running for biochar production. Moreover, this measure may provide the smallest share of additional benefits as compared to the currently still very high costs. We included this measure in our portfolio since the production of biochar is the only measure that ensures persistent C storage and sequestration. All other measures need to be continued in order to keep the additionally stored SOC and even when management is maintained climate change may endanger these additional SOC stocks.

We focussed therefore on measures with expected multiple benefits. Agroforestry and woody vegetation in agricultural landscapes is such an option with strong synergies and therefore also part of the EU biodiversity strategy. In some European countries also in the GAP national targets are set

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to increase the share of agricultural woody vegetation. However, these current ambitions are low compared to what is agreed on in the EU biodiversity strategy. The high potential C sequestration impact of woody feature may help to foster their implementation.

Other measures implemented as part of agricultural cropping practice such as reduced or no tillage, more fodder legumes and cover crops heavily rely on the year of implementation in order to achieve significant C sequestration impacts. All of them have rather low EFs but can be implemented on differently large areas. Here, the potential and realised area of implementation will determine how much these measures can potentially and actually contribute to climate mitigation.

Crop residue management and irrigation are the most constraint measures since crop residues are almost all returned to the soil. Thus, only the small fraction of crop residues that are actually burned or used for other purposes define the potential area of implementation. For irrigation it's the availability of water and irrigation infrastructure that is strongly limiting the expansion of this management option.

C sequestration potentials in European agriculture need to be bound to well tested and established measures in order to be feasible and realistic for the next decades. The key is the implementation of the measures at large scale. Thus, besides climate and environmental benefits, economic benefits and incentives will be crucial in order to convert this potential C sequestration as outlined in this study into a realised C sequestration.

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Annex

Notes from Online Workshops

ZERO TILLAGE

Synonym
No-til, no-tillage

Definition
System of planting crops into untilled soil by opening a narrow slot, trench or broadcast width and () obtain proper seed coverage. No other soil

Reference
Inversion tillage (synonyms: ploughing; conventional tillage)

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

- Increased nitrogen content
- Lower erosion risk
- reduced fuel and machinery cost
- less working time
- lower CO₂ release to atmosphere
- Improved soil structure
- Soil water conservation
- weeds and diseases
- reduced water availability for the crops due to less tillage
- Soil compaction
- not very compatible with legume forage
- crop establishment is very slow
- dry years with low residue reduction
- conversion time to successful no-tillage
- Proper machinery
- purchase of seed drill
- Increased pesticide use
- low yields, lower profit
- costs, production costs per hectare tend to be lower than for the current system

constraints

- bio-physical: Weeds, Pests and diseases, reduced water availability for the crops due to less tillage, Soil compaction
- technical: Conversion time to successful no-tillage, Proper machinery, dry years with low residue reduction, not reliable in farming with high water needs? - Competition will need to be reduced by tillage
- economic: purchase of seed drill, Increased pesticide use, low yields, lower profit, costs, production costs per hectare tend to be lower than for the current system

Area of implementation
All of today's agricultural land, which is used for annual crops and subject to regular inversion tillage

Implementation intensity
Stop any tillage activity completely

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- Eurostat (average values for NUTS2 administrative regions)

Conventional tillage

Percent of cropland

Zero tillage

Percent of cropland

Conservational tillage

Percent of cropland

"Conventional tillage involves intensive ploughing and harrowing with a tractor, which leads to a total inversion of the soil."

"Zero tillage means that the soil is not tilled at all."

"Conservation tillage, on the other hand, tries to minimise soil disturbance and leave most of the crop residues on the surface."

Open issues

- Eurostat allow to estimate the average share of conventional tillage, conventional tillage and zero tillage in crop rotation: NUTS2 region. If we convert this sequence of tillage events to exclusively no-til, could we say how much SOC will be sequestered?
- How to treat agricultural land with a certain share of reduced (conservation) tillage in crop rotations?
- If we continue with Eurostat data, how to deal with countries without data?
- Data from the German Agricultural Soil Inventory suggests tillage and the mode of seedbed preparation to depend on crop types (see figure below). How feasible is it to ban all tillage activities from European agricultural land?

In many region the feasibility will be very low (Green)

Legend: No till (Green), Non-invasive tillage (Blue), Invasive tillage (Red)

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REDUCED TILLAGE

Decision:
Change name to "non-inversion" tillage

Synonym
Minimum tillage?

Definition
Non-inversion

Reference
Inversion tillage (synonyms: ploughing; conventional tillage)

In WP2 we worked with non-inversion tillage and not with reduced or minimum tillage. We thought that is a clearer definition. We could then also investigate the impact of tillage depth when calculating EF (Greet)

WP2 used for non-inversion the Eurostat definition, i.e. Tillage operation that does not involve the inversion of the soil. (Greet)

I would also recommend to add to the definition: 'no inversion tillage throughout the entire crop rotation' (Greet)

Corina: mostly only to 30 cm but not 100%

Ulter et al: maybe include machinery types in the definition? Include conservation tillage as a term?

Lower erosion risk reduced fuel and machinery cost less working time

Soil water conservation improved soil structure

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

bio-physical

Soil compaction Weeds Pests and diseases

technical

crop establishment in very wet soils Conversion time to successful reduced tillage Proper machinery dry years with low residue reduction

economic

purchase of suitable cultivator Increased pesticide use overall, production costs per hectare tend to be lower than for the control system

Area of implementation
All of today's agricultural land, which is used for annual crops and is currently subject to regular inversion tillage

Implementation intensity
Stop any conventional inversion tillage and restrict tillage to non-inversion, reduced tillage

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- See no-till (left)

Open issues

- How about areas with zero tillage today?

Agree for non-inversion tillage (Greet), maybe not easy but feasible in most cases

for constraints (future publications) see Bijttebier et al. 2018 for constraints in 5 EU countries <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.05.044>

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IRRIGATION

Synonym
-

Definition

The artificial watering of the land for the purpose of growing crops.

Reference

Rain-fed cropping

Data available for mapping the area of implementation
 • Eurostat (average values for NUTS2 administrative regions)

"The **irrigated area** measures the actual amount of land irrigated and can vary significantly from year to year due to, for instance, meteorological conditions or the choice of crop."
 "The **irrigable area** is the area which is equipped for irrigation. This area does not show so much variation from year to year as it is costly for the farmer to invest in irrigation equipment."

"Cultivated land parcels under agricultural use for arable crops that are permanently or periodically irrigated, using a permanent infrastructure (irrigation channels, drainage network and additional irrigation facilities). Most of these crops cannot be cultivated without artificial water supply. Does not include sporadically irrigated land. Excludes rice fields."

Open issues

- How to define the "irrigable area"?
 - Approach 1: Use Eurostat data. But: Turkey missing; only available at NUTS2 level
 - Approach 2: Evaluate time series of Corine data. For each grid cell, check whether this has been irrigated at least once in the Corine time series. If yes, define as irrigable land.
- In practice, especially outside the Mediterranean, irrigation tends to be crop and year/weather specific. The Corine data might allow for each pixel to evaluate the proportion of years each grid cell was irrigated. Would there be data to estimate emission factors also for only occasionally irrigated land?

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COVER CROPS

Synonym
Intermediate crop; Catch crops (to lower N leaching); Green manure (to increase N availability)

Definition
Introduction of additional cover crops within existing crop rotations to cover temporarily bare soils, as in e.g. bare winter fallows

Reference
Cropland with temporarily bare soil

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

- attraction of insects
- increase nitrogen availability
- weed control
- improve soil structure
- beautification of the agricultural landscape
- less nitrogen leaching
- Lower erosion risk
- biodeversity

constraints

- bio-physical**
 - Growing season needs to be long enough: # at least 40 days > 5°C after harvest of main crop until first frost; # precipitation > potential evaporation
 - Water availability for the next crop might be compromised
- technical**
 - Not suitable if bare fallow period is too short
 - not possible when winter crops are grown (e.g. winter wheat) (Gruel)
- economic**
 - Average 136€/ha for seeds, establishment, mulching

Area of implementation
All of today's agricultural land, which is used for annual crops and characterized by temporarily bare soil

Implementation intensity
Cover all bare soil in crop rotations with cover crops, where bio-physically possible

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- Eurostat** (average values for NUTS2 administrative regions)

Soil cover during winter:	Legend
Bare soil	Percent of cropland: 0-60
Cover crops	Percent of cropland: 0-30
Winter crop	Percent of cropland: 0-80
Plant residues	Percent of cropland: 0-80

Soil cover during winter: Bare soil

"an area of arable land that is ploughed or otherwise tilled in autumn and is not sown or covered during winter with any plant residues, remaining bare until the pre-seeding or seeding agro-technical operations in the following spring period. Arable land on which tillage methods leave more than 10% of plant residues on the surface are recorded under "plant residues" "

Soil cover during winter: Cover crops

"an area of arable land on which plants are sown specifically to reduce the loss of soil, nutrients and plant protection products during the winter or other periods when the land would otherwise be bare and susceptible to losses. The economic interest of these crops is low, and the main goal is soil and nutrient protection. Normally they are ploughed in during spring before sowing another crop, and are not harvested or used for grazing. Agricultural land with no plant cover or where there are just plant residues on the top is especially vulnerable to soil erosion and nutrient and pesticide loss. In efforts to reduce losses which are harmful both to the environment and to the economy one of the most efficient tools is keeping the land covered with plants at all times. These crops should not be mistaken for normal winter crops or grassland."

Soil cover during winter: Winter crop

"an area of arable land on which crops are sown in the autumn and growing during the winter (normal winter crops, such as winter wheat), normally harvested or used for grazing"

Soil cover during winter: Plant residues

"an area of arable land covered with the plant residues and stubble of the previous crop season during winter, intermediate and cover crops are excluded. Plants residues can be straw, stubble or other plants parts leaving good mulch (for example sugar beet leaves) regardless if they remain from the previous harvest or have been added by the farmer. Potatoes are normally excluded because the stalks are degraded too quickly. The tillage operations are in this case normally carried out in the spring. Certain tillage operations can be carried out in autumn, if they leave enough plant residues on the surface. Such tillage methods could be chisel or disk ploughing or similar. The straw can be removed for energy or other purposes, but an indicative threshold for remaining residue is minimum 10%. Self-grown cereals cover the soil following a tillage operation is included"

- Remote sensing data as readily provided by e.g. [ecodatacube](#) to identify bare soils during winter based on their NDVI values
 - Pre-tests for German cropland were promising (n=24,917 site years). From October to December, sites with bare soil showed significantly lower NDVI values than sites with winter crops or cover crops (see below)
 - Data available for all target countries with the exception of Turkey

Soil cover during winter in German cropland (BZE data; n = 24,917 site years)

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CROP ROTATIONS

Synonym

-

The four mentioned crop types are very different. Are there enough experimental data to cover all and to combine them to one measure?

Definition

Replacing one or more low protein crops in the crop rotation with high-protein crops (clovergrass, soy

I would talk more on limiting the share of these crops (not sure the experiment increase the duration of these crop in the rotation...)

alfalfa)

Lupinus? Maybe mention Fabaceae and each country will have its own more adequate species? (A. Paz)

hick peas and other beans for human consumption?

Better distinguish between different types of legume crops (Greet) less carbon is expected from soy or beans than from clover or alfalfa (see analysis below)

I suggest we talk with sonja keel (greet)

We still want to add another practice: have more crops in the rotation with higher carbon input. See earlier suggestions. (Greet)

Only include clovergrass and alfalfa? But does not fit everywhere. Should it Fabaceae?

Reference

Common, current crop rotations (business as usual)

bio-physical

Depends on the crop types and could be soil types, climate, water availability

constraints

technical

Suitable machinery for sowing and harvesting should be available.

Experiences with the management techniques (e.g. fertilisation, silage etc) could be lacking.

economic

There needs to be a profitable market for the crop or it should be interesting to use as feed for the farm animals; the profits or nutritional value need to be the same or better than the crop it is replacing.

Costs for seeds, machinery (or contractor with right machinery) and fertilizers and market prices should be compared with the crop the new crop is replacing

Area of implementation

All of today's agricultural land, which is used for annual crops and ???

Implementation intensity

???

Greet: Suggestion is to start from current relative share of crops grown in an area and have a questionnaire to the individual countries to estimate to what extent they expect some crops can be replaced by crops with higher carbon input. Depends on EF analysis of task 2.2 and interaction with WP9 - to discuss further in Rome.

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- [For each crop type, Eurostat](#) informs about the area under cultivation (aggregated for NUTS2 administrative regions)

- Wait for European crop type maps to be released soon?

- LPIS data (where available)

Is Jan Peter Lesschen consulted on EU data? (Greet)

Open issues

- Agree on a final definition of the measure, considering the data available

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CROP RESIDUE MANAGEMENT

Synonym - what do we mean with "additional"? (Greet)

Definition - Additional plant parts that are not harvested as main product but left on the soil surface or incorporated into the topsoil.

Reference - Removal of crop residues and no return of harvested residues with organic amendments (Aurb)

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

- improved soil structure
- protection against runoff and sediment loss
- more and better nutrient availability
- improved soil biodiversity

Notes:

- Do we need to be more specific? What kind of crops will we consider? (Greet)
- Do we need to consider animals in soil? Will there be any other animals? Factors that increase the soil's ability to store carbon? (Greet)
- Do we need to consider animals in soil? Will there be any other animals? Factors that increase the soil's ability to store carbon? (Greet)
- Do we need to consider animals in soil? Will there be any other animals? Factors that increase the soil's ability to store carbon? (Greet)

constraints

- bio-physical**: C/N ratio of crops grown, low clay content of soil
- technical**: suitable machinery needs to be available, increase of weeds and plant pathogens
- economic**: reduced yields, income loss if straw is not sold - price for straw in Austria 15-20€ per 100 kg, price for incorporation (120€/ha), price for removal (70-75€/ha), depending on farm type crop residues might be fed to own cattle

Other notes:

- How effective is straw mulching in increasing SOC storage? Also, compared to producing straw biochar.

Area of implementation ?

Implementation intensity ?

Note: All of today's agricultural land, where crop residues are burnt regularly on the field or exported to be burnt elsewhere (e.g. in power plants).

• National emission inventories of greenhouse gases for UNFCCC

TABLE 3.F SECTORAL BACKGROUND DATA FOR AGRICULTURE

Field burning of agricultural residues⁽¹⁾

(Sheet 1 of 1)

Inventory 2020
Submission 2022 v1
SPAIN

SOURCE, FUEL, GAS CONVERSION AND SINK CATEGORIES	ACTIVITY DATA AND OTHER RELATED INFORMATION				IMPLIED EMISSION FACTORS		EMISSIONS	
	Area burned (k ha/yr)	Biomass available ⁽²⁾ (t dm/ha)	Combustion factor	Total biomass burned ⁽³⁾ (kt dm)	CH ₄ (kg T dm)	N ₂ O	CH ₄ (kt)	N ₂ O

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AGROFORESTRY WITH HEDGES / HEDGEROW

Synonym

Definition

Additional planting of lines of shrubs or small trees, often forming a boundary or fence.

Reference

Cropland without hedges

Asel shrubs can be combined with trees (also larger trees)

Light hedges are usually managed in some way, could be included in the definition.

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

Area of implementation

All of today's cropland (annual + perennial) area, where additional trees / bushes could grow

Implementation intensity

1% of that area

How to justify this number?
we probably could use LPS field boundaries and that we know the total length of field boundaries (Grove)

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- Copernicus tree cover density on agricultural land as illustrated [here](#)

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ALLEY-CROPPING AGROFORESTRY

Synonym

-

Definition

Planting of single trees on cropland in lines within the field (covering between 10-15% of the field).

No short rotation coppices with lifecycles < about 20 to 25 years

Reference

Cropland without trees

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- Copernicus tree cover density on agricultural land as illustrated [here](#)

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CONVERSION OF CROPLAND TO GRASSLAND

Synonym

Definition

Land-use change from cropland to grassland

Reference

Cropland

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

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CONVERSION OF GRASSLAND TO SILVOPASTURE

Synonym

Definition

Land use change from grassland to silvopasture

Pasture and meadows?

Reference

Permanent grassland without silvopasture

co-benefits beyond SOC sequestration

Area of implementation

All of today's permanent grassland area, where additional trees could grow

Implementation intensity

1% of that area

As for agroforestry measures?

Data available for mapping the area of implementation

- CORINE land cover and other remote sensing data

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